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muhimdir. Sun'iy intellektning ta'limga integratsiyalashuviga ehtiyotkorlik bilan yondashish va uning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari o'rtasida muvozanatni saqlash kerak, bu talabalar va butun ta'lim tizimi uchun foydali bo'lishi kerak.

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EXPLORATION OF ETHNIC MUSIC ELEMENTS IN CHINESE PIANO WORKS

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Annotation. *The traditional Chinese music culture is vast and profound, and the elements of Chinese ethnic music shape the development process and inheritance concept of Chinese civilization. By exploring different types of Chinese ethnic music elements, we can better express the cultural core of Chinese piano works that is completely different from Western piano art, and thus create piano pieces with more ethnic characteristics. The reasonable integration of ethnic music elements into piano creation will reflect the uniqueness of Chinese piano works, thereby achieving effective integration of Eastern and Western music. This not only enhances the ethnic characteristics of the works themselves, but also enhances the influence of Chinese music culture in the world art field.*

Key words: *traditional, Chinese music, culture, piano, world art.*

Аннотация. *Традиционная китайская музыкальная культура обширна и глубока, а элементы китайской этнической музыки определяют процесс развития и концепцию наследования китайской цивилизации. Изучая различные типы элементов китайской этнической музыки, мы можем лучше выразить культурное ядро китайских фортепианных произведений, которое полностью отличается от западного фортепианного искусства, и таким образом создать фортепианные произведения с более этническими характеристиками. Разумная интеграция элементов этнической музыки в фортепианное творчество отразит уникальность китайских фортепианных произведений, тем самым достигнув эффективной интеграции восточной и западной музыки. Это не только повышает этнические характеристики самих произведений, но и усиливает влияние китайской музыкальной культуры на мировое искусство.*

Ключевые слова: *традиционная, китайская музыка, культура, фортепиано, мировое искусство.*

Annotatsiya. *An'anaviy Xitoy musiqa madaniyati keng va chuqurdir va Xitoy etnik musiqasining elementlari Xitoy sivilizatsiyasining rivojlanish jarayoni va meros kontseptsiyasini shakllantiradi. Xitoy etnik musiqasi elementlarining har xil turlarini o'rganish orqali biz G'arb pianino san'atidan butunlay farq qiladigan xitoylik pianino asarlarining madaniy o'zagini yaxshiroq ifodalashimiz va shu tariqa ko'proq etnik xususiyatlarga ega pianino qismlarini yaratishimiz mumkin. Etnik musiqa elementlarini pianino yaratishga oqilona integratsiyalashuvi Xitoy pianino asarlarining o'ziga xosligini aks ettiradi va shu bilan Sharq va G'arb musiqasining samarali integratsiyasiga erishadi. Bu nafaqat asarlarning etnik xususiyatlarini oshiradi, balki Xitoy musiqa madaniyatining jahon san'ati sohasidagi ta'sirini kuchaytiradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *an'anaviy, xitoy musiqasi, madaniyati, pianino, jahon san'ati.*

China's ethnic music has a long history of development, dating back to the Western Zhou Dynasty to the Spring and Autumn Period and the Warring States Period, with various traditional musical forms such as playing the sheng, guqin, and qin. According to their different themes and artistic characteristics, they can be roughly divided into folk songs, rap music, song

and dance music, opera music, comprehensive music genres, and ethnic instrumental music, etc. Each type of music has different genres, diverse forms, and rich works.

In Chinese piano works, ethnic music elements mainly include melody, mode, rhythm, harmony, and other aspects. With the continuous development of piano art in our country, the integration of ethnic music elements has become increasingly important. I will explore the ethnic music elements of Chinese piano works from the following aspects.

1. The integration of ethnic languages

Language is the main carrier of national culture, and the Chinese nation has formed a unique language system over thousands of years of development. Integrating national language into piano works can effectively bridge the emotional distance between the public and piano art, making it easier to evoke emotional resonance and build a bridge of communication between the audience and music works. For example, in the representative work of Chinese piano music, "Flower Drum", the ethnic language form of Fengyang Flower Drum Opera is appropriately integrated, and cheerful rhythms and local dialects are incorporated into the work, making the entire piece convey more joyful and lively emotions. For example, in the piano music work "Yellow River Concerto", the creator incorporates the language form of "shouting the horn" into the piano art work, which is highly in line with the language expression habits of people in the Loess Plateau region. It is rough and high pitched, and also demonstrates the determination and courage of the people to save the country generously under the slogan of resistance against Japan and national salvation during times of national crisis.

2. The integration of ethnic musical instruments

In the development of traditional ethnic music culture, musical instruments are an important carrier and expression of culture. Incorporating ethnic instruments with Chinese characteristics into piano music can create a more aesthetically pleasing musical atmosphere, which is more likely to resonate with the audience's emotions and enhance the influence and infectiousness of the music. For example,

The piano music piece "Picking Tea and Plucking Butterflies" incorporates traditional ethnic percussion instruments, imitating the timbre and sound of Chinese folk dances and various Chinese instruments. Through techniques such as timbre imitation and intensity application, it creates a happy and relaxed atmosphere for the tea picking girl while working. This piece successfully showcases the charm of Chinese folk music to audiences around the world through piano performance. The piano music piece "Watching the Opera" incorporates traditional gong and drum instruments, blending them with the piano. Through the insertion of gong and drum points in the prelude, interlude, and epilogue of the music, a warm atmosphere for watching the opera is created, which can better highlight the lively and cheerful rhythm. It achieves the collision and fusion of different instruments in different cultural backgrounds, improving the infectiousness of the work. For example, in the creation of the piano work "Plum Blossom Sannong", the playing techniques of the ancient Chinese musical instrument Guqin were imitated, creating an ethereal atmosphere and expressing sorrowful emotions throughout the work. For example, in the piano work "Sunset Flute and Drum", traditional Chinese instruments such as the xiao, guqin, pipa, and guzheng are imitated, and the piano is used to express traditional folk music. This can create a more innovative auditory experience, enhance the level and expressiveness of the work.

In the process of integrating Chinese and Western music, the integration of ethnic instruments can enrich the expression of piano art, enhance musical communication and integration between instruments, and add new features to piano music works.

3. The integration of ethnic melodies

Melody, as the most fundamental element of music, is reflected by piano composers in the process of creating piano works from the aspects of music content, style, genre, and ethnic characteristics. The use of ethnic song melodies, transplantation or adaptation of ethnic music, and the use of ethnic music melody characteristics in the creation of these three forms are the methods of applying Chinese ethnic melody elements to piano creation.

In the process of piano creation, folk song melody is a crucial factor. For example, Huang Huwei used the melody of Sichuan folk songs as the theme of his creation when creating the large-scale piano suite "Painting of Bashu", which consists of six unique pieces. He used the melody of folk songs to create this piano piece. This form of transplanting or adapting the melodies of folk songs can present traditional Chinese ethnic music more fully on the world stage, allowing people around the world to understand traditional Chinese folk music through the artistic expression of piano, thereby promoting the perfect integration of Chinese and Western cultures.

4. The integration of ethnic modes

In Chinese ethnic music, different ethnic music has different mode characteristics, and mode is an important feature to judge the characteristics of different ethnic music. For example, the overall mode of ethnic music in northern Shaanxi is rough and powerful, the mode of ethnic music in Dai is graceful and ethereal, and the mode of music in Xinjiang is more lively and rhythmic. Traditional Chinese opera is the most important manifestation of mode, and incorporating traditional Chinese opera modes into piano works has become one of the important creative ideas. For example, in Mr. Ding Shande's "Overture in G-flat Major", the modes of Kunqu opera are integrated to express a subtle and vivid emotional tone. The tone and rhythm of Kunqu opera are integrated into piano performance, reflecting the characteristics of Jiangnan music and making the audience feel beautiful and exquisite. For example, the piano piece "Pi Huang" is a solo piano piece created by contemporary Chinese composer Zhang Chao. It is also one of the works that has achieved high artistic expression in contemporary Chinese piano music by using Peking Opera music materials. The work is created using the traditional Chinese opera board style variation technique, drawing on the singing tone of Peking Opera, and using variation forms to integrate elements of Peking Opera into the piano piece, making the entire piece have strong national characteristics and high artistic value. It is a relatively successful piano work with Chinese charm.

Beijing Opera, as a quintessence of our country, has Xipi and Erhuang as its main types of modes. These two opera modes can provide a creative structure for emotional expression from a high and low perspective in piano composition, thereby more vividly showcasing the characteristics of piano music works.

5. The integration of ethnic harmony

Harmony is an important discipline in music that involves the three-dimensional structure and vertical integration of polyphonic music. It is the foundation for the organic development of vocal parts and belongs to important musical vocabulary. The use of harmony can reflect the artistic expression and national style of musical works. The application of traditional harmony is mainly based on the stacking of third degrees, while ethnic harmony

often uses the stacking of fourth and fifth degrees to construct harmony colors, displaying an ancient sound effect with Chinese ethnic charm, conveying a ethereal atmosphere to the audience; In the application of ethnic harmony in our country, there is also the use of second degree stacking, which can create a special atmosphere and even display a sound color with percussion effects. For example, the ending of the piano piece "Guessing the Key" uses a minor second degree, which creates a humorous effect that will be displayed in people's minds; The piano piece "Picking Tea and Flying Butterflies" uses a fifth interval to play the music, and adds high pitched chords to stimulate the listener's inner emotions through harmony; In the piano adaptation "Two Springs Reflecting the Moon", in order to fully showcase the melancholic and melancholic musical emotions, the author uses a second fold arrangement of seventh and ninth chords in the use of harmony.

6. The integration of ethnic music forms

The complexity and diversity of musical structures are the main characteristics of traditional Chinese music. In the process of creating piano music works, structures such as single section, multi section, complex, cyclic, and continuous can all be referenced. The musical form of piano music will also undergo certain changes due to the introduction of ethnic music elements. Among them, the repeated sentence form is one of the more famous forms in China. This type of form mainly allows the first half to be freely varied, while the second half cannot be changed. In the process of piano music creation, applying this type of form can make the music more flexible. For example, the famous musician Li Yinghai used the use of repetition in the process of creating "Sunset Flute and Drum", making the entire piano piece more lively and lively. In addition, musicians actively referenced China's Taoist culture and created a unique musical form when creating piano music works, showing the vigorous creativity of Chinese musicians. While inheriting traditional ethnic culture, they also promoted the rapid development of piano music and made tremendous contributions to the development of world music.

The development of piano in our country is not only integrating traditional music elements of our own nation, but also constantly drawing on excellent Western music culture, presenting a new form of music to the world. Chinese musicians have created many piano works with Chinese characteristics, fully showcasing the ancient national atmosphere of China. The reasonable integration of Chinese ethnic music elements in piano works is crucial for the development of piano art, the inheritance of ethnic culture, and even the integration of Eastern and Western cultures. It is conducive to the creation of piano works, highlighting the style and charm of ethnic music, promoting the inheritance and innovation of ethnic culture, facilitating the integration of Chinese and Western music cultures, creating conditions for dialogue and integration between music cultures, and promoting the exchange and integration of Chinese and Western cultures.

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